

Questionnaire for Landslide Vulnerability

The following questionnaire is a crucial phase of this study which has as main object the development of an integrated vulnerability tool addressing flood risk, seismic risk, landslide risk and building energy efficiency.

This tool should be able to indicate what the overall vulnerability of a building is, for the purpose of more effective management of interventions.

The developed methodology that can be valid for:

- residential building typology present in Algeria, and in particular for the area of the Wadi Abiod Valley;
- buildings with features similar to the one present in Algeria located in areas of the Globe subject to seismic, flood, and landslide risks, where targeted interventions for energy efficiency need to be implemented.

For the purpose of this assessment, individual vulnerabilities (called V_S , V_F , V_L , V_E in the diagram below) will first be assessed.

At the preliminary stage of the study, based on the relevant literature, the main factors affecting individual vulnerabilities toward seismic, flood, landslide risks and energy efficiency were identified. Then, these factors have been expertly grouped into categories.

With this questionnaire, we ask you, as experts, to give a weight to the individual vulnerability factors and categories that is representative of the factor or category importance in defining the total vulnerability of the building.

For clarity, the diagram below summarizes the steps identified for the individual vulnerability assessment.

Once the weights to each category and factor have been determined, the weight of the individual factor will be given by the product of the weight of the category and the weight of the factor within that category.

In particular, the individual vulnerability of the building (V_S , V_F , V_L , V_E) will be given by the following formula:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n P_i * \sum_{j=1}^m p_{i,j} * v_{i,j}$$

Where:

- P_i is the weight of the category i
- $p_{i,j}$ is the weight of the factor j within category i
- $v_{i,j}$ is the value of the factor j within category i (appropriately reclassified on a scale from 0 to 1)
- n is the total number of categories.
- m is the total number of factors within each category

Finally, the individual vulnerabilities for each risk will be integrated based on their respective hazards. This integration will allow for a comprehensive understanding of the building's overall vulnerability profile. The result can be used by decision-makers to prioritize mitigation efforts and allocate resources effectively to enhance the resilience of the building against various hazards.

Instructions for Questionnaire Completion

In what follows, you will first be provided with a description of the individual categories and the related factors identified for your risk. Then, you will be provided with an outline where you can provide your judgment and any comments and/or suggestions.

The following steps are recommended for completing the questionnaire:

1. First read the entire questionnaire, without thinking about assigning any values. This step serves to gain an overview of the problem in all its components.
2. Carefully reread the definitions of categories and factors.
3. Only then to associate a weight with each category (P_i), such that the sum of the category weights is equal to 1.
4. Next, we ask you to associate a weight ($p_{i,j}$) to the factors contained in each category, according to the criterion that within each category the sum of the weights should be equal to 1.

Note: in the COMMENTS section you should enter reason for choosing a weight value, whereas, in the SUGGESTIONS section you should enter eventual suggestions of any kind, including changes that you deem necessary (e.g., other factors to be considered, factors to be neglected, how the define the factor, etc...).

IT IS IMPORTANT THAT ANY CHOICES OR COMMENTS BE ARGUED, SO THAT THIS INFORMATION CAN BE PROVIDED TO THE POOL OF EXPERTS INVOLVED, WHO MAY MODIFY OR CONFIRM THEIR INITIAL JUDGMENT, AT A SECOND STAGE OF THE INVESTIGATION.

LANDSLIDE VULNERABILITY INDEX

Category 1: Structural characteristics of the building.

Structural characteristics refer to the physical attributes and properties of a building or structure that contribute to its stability, strength, and resilience.

Weight Category 1 (P1)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

Category 2: Geographical features

Geographical features of a building refer to the characteristics of its location and surroundings.

Weight Category 2 (P2)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

Category 3: Maintenance characteristics

Maintenance characteristics for buildings encompass various factors related to the upkeep, preservation, and management of the structure over time.

Weight Category 3 (P3)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

Category 1: Structural characteristics of the building.

- **Year of Construction**

The year of construction factor refers to the year of completion.

Weight Factor 1 (p ₁₁)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Roof Design**

Roof design refers to the architectural and structural features of the roof of a building. For example, roof slope prevents material from getting accumulated at top of building.

Weight Factor 2 (p ₁₂)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Foundation Type**

Foundation type refers to the construction materials used to support a building's structure.

Weight Factor 3 (p ₁₃)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Foundation Depth**

Foundation depth is expressed as the length of the foundation below the ground. Foundation depth reflects the capability to resist displacement as deeper foundation offers higher resistance.

Weight Factor 4 (p ₁₄)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Horizontal configuration of building**

The horizontal configuration of a building refers to its layout or arrangement in a horizontal plane, typically viewed from above. It encompasses factors such as the shape, size, and arrangement of the building's footprint and floor plan.

Weight Factor 5 (p ₁₅)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Structural Typology**

Different structural typology will experience different levels of damage depending on the intensity of the landslide.

Weight Factor 6 (p ₁₆)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Number of Floors**

This means the number of floors above ground.

Weight Factor 7 (p ₁₇)	
Comments	

Suggestions	
-------------	--

- **Presence of basement**

Basement floors are the floors located in the underground level of a building.

Weight Factor 8 (p ₁₈)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

Category 2: Georgical features

- **Surrounding wall of building**

The surrounding wall of a building refers to the exterior walls that enclose and define the perimeter of the structure. It provides protection to the building from the intrusion of the landslide material. Vulnerability varies according to the different construction material of the wall, if present.

Weight Factor 1 (p ₂₁)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Distance between two houses from each other**

It is defined as the distance between two houses.

Weight Factor 2 (p ₂₂)	
Comments	

Suggestions	
-------------	--

- **Slope Side**

Description of the side of the building facing the slope (e.g., the propensity of the building to be damaged by landslides varies if the building side is facing a wall or a window)

Weight Factor 3 (p ₂₃)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

Category 3: Maintenance characteristics

- **Type of construction**

Type of construction refers to the method used in building the structure. This includes whether the building was constructed according to established design practices or if it was self-constructed using traditional methods.

Weight Factor 1 (p ₃₁)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Quality of construction**

The quality of construction refers to the overall standard of materials used and their adherence to building codes and regulations.

Weight Factor 2 (p ₃₂)	
Comments	

Suggestions	
-------------	--

- **State of maintenance**

The state of maintenance indicates whether the building is kept in good condition through regular maintenance and repair activities, or if it shows signs of neglect or deterioration due to lack of care.

Weight Factor 3 (p ₃₃)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Cracks in Structures**

Cracks in structures are fractures or openings that develop in building materials such as concrete, masonry, or plaster. They can vary in size, shape, and severity. Addressing cracks in a timely manner through proactive maintenance and repair measures is essential to preserve the structural integrity, functionality, and appearance of the building, as well as ensure the safety and well-being of its occupants.

Weight Factor 4 (p ₃₄)	
Comments	
Suggestions	